

SELF ESTEEM OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS: A GENDER PERSPECTIVE

Dr Lubna J. Mansuri

Associate Professor,

Bombay Teachers' Training College, Mumbai, India

Abstract

Self- esteem is a feeling of self-appreciation and is an indispensable emotion for people to adapt to the society and live their lives. For adolescents in particular environment in which they are raised contributes profoundly to the development of their self-esteem. The paper aims to compare the self- esteem of secondary school students of SSC and CBSE board. The total sample consisted of 400 students (192 girls and 208 boys) respectively. The statistical technique used for the study was t- test. The methodology of the study was of descriptive method of comparative type. The sampling technique used was simple random sampling.

It is imperative to keep a tab on the self -esteem of adolescents in schools as that forms the basis to their mental health, character and personality as mature adults. The researcher attempts to acquire a clearer picture of the sense of self appreciation and self-esteem the youngsters of this generation across various boards possess. The findings of the study were that there is a gender wise significant difference between the self- esteem of boys and girls of SSC and CBSE board. The girls of SSC board possess a higher level of self- esteem as compared to girls of CBSE board and The self- esteem of SSC boys is high as compared to boys of CBSE board. Self-esteem is important because higher self-esteem is associated with high efficiency, academic achievements, high and accurate decision-making skills, greater ability to work in groups, while self- esteem is one of the major repairing force behind any damage caused.

Keywords: *Self- Esteem, secondary school students, Gender (boys & Girls) SSC & CBSE Boards*

Aarhat Publication & Aarhat Journals is licensed Based on a work at <http://www.aarhat.com/erj/>

Introduction:

Adolescents see themselves in different lights from time to time - there are feelings of fulfillment & appreciation to loathing and helplessness towards oneself. Self- esteem is a feeling of self-appreciation and is an indispensable emotion for people to adapt to the society and live their lives. For adolescents in particular environment in which they are raised contributes profoundly to the development of their self-esteem.

For every school going student, self-esteem plays a major role even as a member of a family and the dynamics one shares with each of one's relations are majorly influenced by it. At the same time, damaged self-esteem serves as a stepping stone to many forms of psychological and sociological setbacks which in turn harm the child and those around them. The 21st-century has posed a considerable challenge to the fine balance between an individual self-esteem and sense of fulfillment.

Self- esteem reflects an individual's overall subjective emotional evaluation of his or her own worth. It is a well -

known fact that individuals with a high self -esteem in childhood are likely to be adults with high self- esteem. Many studies have demonstrated that during middle and late adolescence, and into early adulthood, self- esteem stabilizes or even increases. Especially in adolescents, the worse they feel about themselves, the worse they often treat others, the worse they get treated in return, the worse they end up feeling about themselves. Thus, the cycle continues.

Need of the study

Evaluating self-esteem of adolescents can be an important factor that determines their overall growth. It can also be an effective method for understanding their past and present circumstances as well as considering treatment for children with psychosomatic disorders. Self- esteem has deeply been associated with sense of satisfaction and fulfillment and lack of it leads to many issues such as suicidal tendencies, depression, destructive relationships, violent behavior and earlier initiation of sexual activities. It is imperative to keep a tab on the self -esteem of adolescents in schools as that forms the basis to their mental health, character and personality as mature adults. The researcher attempts to acquire a clearer picture of the sense of self appreciation and self-esteem the youngsters of this generation across various boards possess.

The researcher felt the need to conduct a study on the level of self -esteem among secondary school students. There is a great scope of development in this area since not many researches have been conducted in this arena. This research would go a long way in identifying and diagnosing those individuals in need of critical help as it reflects not only on those individuals' overall growth but also on the society in general.

Review of Related Literature

Bhardwaj and Agrawal (2013) studied the self-esteem of the pre-adolescent children and saw the gender differences between males and females in that early age. The sample consisted of 50 males and 50 females' students with ages between 9 and 12 years. Students in the study were studying in fifth to seven standards in a school in the North India. Significant differences were not found in social, academic and parental self-esteem, but when data of male participants were compared with the female participants the general self-esteem of females were found to be higher than males.

Joshi, Shobhna and Rekha Srivastava (2009) conducted a research on Self-esteem and Academic Achievement of Adolescents. The study investigated the gender differences in self-esteem and academic achievement of urban and rural adolescents. The sample of this study consisted of 200 urban and 200 rural from Varanasi District. The findings indicated that Urban adolescents scored higher in academic achievement as compared to rural adolescents. Boys scored significantly higher on self-esteem as compared to girls. Significant gender differences were found in academic achievement. Girls were significantly higher on academic achievement as compared to boys.

Dhal, Bhatia & et al (2007) conducted a study on Adolescent Self-Esteem, Attachment and Loneliness. Adolescents (55 males and 55 females) from a public school in Delhi, aged 10-13 years were administered. Adolescents aged 10-11 years reported higher self-esteem as compared to those aged 12-13 years. Adolescents with high self-esteem were securely attached while those with low self-esteem had preoccupied and had fearful attachment. Adolescents studying in a public school reported high levels of self-esteem, moderate loneliness and a secure attachment style. Students with low self-esteem and feelings of loneliness may benefit from psychological intervention.

Concept of Self- Esteem

The term self-esteem is used to describe a person's overall sense of self-worth or personal value. In other words, how much you appreciate and like yourself. Self-esteem is often seen as a personality trait, which means that it tends to be

stable and enduring. Self- esteem can involve a variety of beliefs about yourself, such as the appraisal of your own appearance, beliefs, emotions, and behaviors. Self-esteem can play a significant role in your motivation and success throughout your life. Low self-esteem may hold you back from succeeding at school or work because you don't believe yourself to be capable of success.

By contrast, having a healthy self-esteem can help you achieve because you navigate life with a positive, assertive attitude and believe you can accomplish your goals.

The need for self-esteem plays an important role in psychologist Abraham Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which depicts self-esteem as one of the basic human motivations. Maslow suggested that people need both esteem from other people as well as inner self- respect. Both of these needs must be fulfilled in order for an individual to grow as a person and achieve self-actualization. It is important to note that self-esteem is a concept distinct from self-efficacy, which involves how well you believe you'll handle future actions, performance, or abilities.

Aim of the study

To compare and study the self-esteem of adolescents in SSC and CBSE boards on the basis of their gender.

Objectives of the study

1. To compare the level of self-esteem of secondary school students on the basis of their gender of SSC and CBSE board.

Hypotheses of the study

1. There is no gender wise significant difference between the self-esteem of boys and girls of SSC and CBSE Board
2. There is no gender wise significant difference between the self-esteem of girls of SSC with girls of CBSE Board
3. There is no gender wise significant difference between the self-esteem of boys of SSC with boys of CBSE Board

Conceptual Definitions

1. **Self-esteem:** The positive or negative attitude about self, the degree of liking or satisfaction within self, and owns feeling of perceived worth as compared with others.
2. **Secondary school students:** It refers to the students in the age group of 14 to 16 years and studying in ninth standard.

Sample of the Study

Table 1.1 Gender wise Sample

Gender	SSC Board	CBSE Board	Total
No. of Girls (N)	101	91	192
No. of Boys (N)	99	109	208
Total Sample			400

The total sample of the present study consisted of 400. The total sample of boys were 208 and 109 were from CBSE and 99 of SSC board respectively. The total no of girls were 192 out of which 91 were of CBSE and 101 were from SSC board respectively. The sample collected was from 9th grade.

Methodology of the Study - For the present study, the researcher used the descriptive method of comparative type. The sample was collected from 9th grade students of secondary board.

Simple random sampling technique was used.

Tool of the Study

The researcher used a readymade tool for the data collection. The tool used was developed by Suzanne Harrill Self-Esteem Inventory. The tool consisted of 25 items with scale of 0 to 4 based upon the current thoughts, feelings and behaviors.

Statistical Techniques of the Study

The statistical technique used for the study was t- test.

Findings and Discussions of the Study

H01- There is no gender wise significant difference between the self-esteem of boys and girls of SSC and CBSE Boards

Table 1.2 Relevant Statistics of the self-esteem of Total sample of boys with Total sample of girls from SSC and CBSE Board.

Variable	Group	N	Mean	t-ratio	P value
Self-esteem	Girls	192	60.4531	+3.27	0.000113
	Boys	208	56.8894		

From the Table 1.1 the t-test value is +3.27 and the P value is 0.000113. The P-value is 0.000113 which is less than 0.05. Hence, we conclude that there is a gender wise significant difference between the self- esteem of boys and girls of SSC and CBSE board. The girls had a high level of self- esteem, when compared to boys.

Discussion: This is quite a welcome change wherein the self-esteem of girls is on the higher side when compared to their counterparts. The reasons of this can be attributed to the various Government and Policies to support the girl child. Also, the attitude of the families and the society at large has begun to change. This has led to the inclusion of the girls' opinions and view points in the major decisions pertaining to their lives.

H02-There is no gender wise significant difference between the self-esteem of girls of SSC with girls of CBSE Board Schools.

Table 1.3: Relevant Statistics of the self-esteem of girls of SSC with girls of CBSE Board

Variable	Group	N	Mean	t-ratio	P value
Self-esteem	Girls of SSC	101	68.4752	+13.16	<.0001
	Girls of CBSE	91	51.5495		

From the data given in table 1.2 the t ratio of this comparison is +13.16 while the p value is less than 0.0001. Since the p value is lesser than 0.01, there is a gender wise significant difference between the self- esteems of girls of SSC and CBSE board, because the p value is 0.0001 which is much lesser than 0.01. The girls of SSC board possess a higher level of self- esteem as compared to girls of CBSE board

Discussion: There is major difference in the level of self-esteem of the girl students of SSC board and the girl students of CBSE board students. This means that there are some factors responsible for the prominent difference in their self-esteem. This can be because of the fact that most of the parents of CBSE school belong to Central Government Jobs while parents of SSC Board girls are locally employed. Girls in particular are more connected to their parents and hence frequent transfers may disconnect them from the family leading to low level of self-esteem.

H03- There is no gender wise significant difference between the self-esteem of boys of SSC with boys of CBSE Board

Table 1.4 Relevant Statistics of the self-esteem of boys of SSC with boys of CBSE Board Schools

Variable	Group	N	Mean	t-ratio	P value
Self-esteem	Boys of SSC	99	61.8384	+8.13	<.0001
	Boys of CBSE	109	52.3945		

The data shows the t ratio of this data to be +8.13 white the p value is 0.0001. Since the p value is far lesser than 0.01, there is a significant gender wise difference in the self-esteem of boys of SSC and boys of CBSE board. The self-esteem of SSC boys is high as compared to boys of CBSE board.

Discussion: There is major difference in the level of self-esteem of the boys of SSC board and the boys of CBSE board. This means that there are some factors responsible for the prominent difference in their self-esteem. This can be because of the fact that most of though the infrastructure and other facilities are provided in CBSE school but due to poor maintenance and irregular conduction of classes the academic performance of the boys is much below standards. There is a lengthy procedure in recruiting permanent teachers for a CBSE Board as it falls under the central government. This results in hiring of temporary teachers which are not as dedicated towards the students. These all factors contribute to the low academic performance of boys and hence low self-esteem.

Significance of the study

The study related to the self-esteem of students can be beneficial to the teachers, the parents, the curriculum framers and the administrative heads of the schools.

This study will help the teachers understand the student better as these results act as a warning bell for some and a reiteration of the fact the rest are doing just fine.

The teachers can accommodate the concept of self-esteem in their teaching philosophy so as eliminate the difference in self-esteem on the basis of gender. It acts as a report card of the students and thus help them analyze the remedial measures as required.

The responsibility of parents because they are the single most significant influence in the child's life. With the help of such self-esteem tests, parents can get a microscopic view into the child's thought process.

Such techniques can serve as a very helpful tool and act as a catalyst in bringing back the child's self-esteem, which in-turn will automatically put him in control of his life.

The study will also help the students themselves. Tests on self- esteem go a long way in the making of confident healthy individuals. These tests help you reflect and fathom into one's own being thus creating a conducive environment for self -growth.

The results of a grade help the administrative authorities as well as heads of institutions to effectively foster students' self-esteem and self-concept. It facilitates the Principal in deciding the factors leading to the decrease in the academic performance of the pupils as they mature age wise.

A comparative study between the boards helps the curriculum framers in making changes in the syllabus to inculcate topics and content to foster students' sense of competence and self-worth.

Implications of the Study

The current day and age is filled with challenges for the educators as well as students. While globalization and technology has made this entire world a small town, it has also made the roles of educators so much more challenging. The students have exposure to number of facts thoughts and ideas today. Hence, it is very important that the school takes measures from time to time. Self-esteem is important because higher self-esteem is associated with high efficiency, academic achievements, high and accurate decision-making skills, greater ability to work in groups, while self-esteem is one of the major repairing force behind any damage caused. On the other hand, low levels of self-esteem result in inability to work in groups, depression, anxiety, inability to take appropriate decisions, inability to get back up on the feet, etc. The corrective measures can include various co-curricular activities, debates, singing and dancing competitions, reading assignments, presentations, group discussions, motivational videos, and talks by eminent personalities from time to time.

References:

- Bhardwaj, A., & Agrawal, G. (2013). Gender difference in pre-adolescents' self-esteem. *Int J Soc Sci Interdisc Res*, 8 (2), 114-119
- Dhal, A., Bhatia, S., Sharma, V., & Gupta, P. (2007). Adolescent Self-Esteem, Attachment and Loneliness. *Journal of Indian Association for Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, 3(3), 61-63
- Joshi, S. & Srivastava, R. (2009). Self-esteem and Academic Achievement of Adolescents, *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 35, 33-39.
- http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/33651/7/11_chapter%202.pdf
- <http://www.ijip.in/Archive/v4i4/18.01.046.20170404.pdf>
- <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3779915/>
- http://etd.fcla.edu/CF/CFH0004293/Bauman_Shannon_A_201212_BS.pdf
- <http://ufdcimages.uflib.ufl.edu/CA/00/40/02/54/00001/PDF.pdf>
- https://repository.asu.edu/attachments/150529/content/Wolfe_asu_0010N_14727.pdf
- <http://eprints.utar.edu.my/278/1/PY-2011-0802154.pdf>
- <http://www.iosrjournals.org/iosr-jhss/papers/Vol.%2021%20Issue7/Version-8/G2107085663.pdf>
- <http://alfredadler.edu/sites/default/files/Franz%20MP%202010.pdf>
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/236675348_Self-esteem_and_life_satisfaction_in_adolescents-gender_and_age_as_potential_moderators <http://alfredadler.edu/sites/default/files/Ulrich%20MP%202010.pdf>
- <http://medind.nic.in/jak/t09/s1/jakt09s1p33.pdf>
- <http://www.gjmedph.com/uploads/O3-Vo2No5.pdf>
- <https://psyct.psychopen.eu/article/view/121/html>
- <http://indianresearchjournals.com/pdf/IJSSIR/2017/April/3.pdf>